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EU MISSION PLATFORM | CLIMATE NEUTRAL AND SMART CITIES

TIPS4PED

CEN TC 465 Ad hoc Group

Climate-Neutral Smart Cities and Communities

November 2025

Funded by
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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Acknowledgements:

The dedication of committed volunteers drives standardisation work. Our sincere thanks go to all those who contributed their time, expertise, and enthusiasm to the success of the Ad Hoc Group.

This work was financially supported by **StandICT 2026** (Grant No.101091933), **NetZeroCities** (Grant No. 101139652) and **TIPS4PED** (Grant No. 101139633), funded by the European Commission.

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■ Executive Summary

The CEN/TC 465 Ad hoc Group on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and Communities is established to accelerate the integration of sustainability and digitalisation in European urban development. Convened under the broader mission to align European standardisation with the EU's 2050 climate-neutrality target, the group brings together stakeholders from policy, industry, research, and local governments to translate visionary policy frameworks into actionable standardisation pathways.

Over a ten-month collaborative process, the Ad hoc Group engages in a structured exploration of the synergies between emerging urban innovation practices and existing or needed standards. Through an agile and inclusive working model, the group reviews a wide range of initiatives, policies, and use cases, including eight local case studies from cities across Europe. These case studies and projects highlight the transformative role of digital tools, such as local digital twins, data spaces, and AI, in enabling sustainable urban transformation.

■ Key Outcomes and Contributions

- ▶ **Integrated Knowledge Base:** The group consolidates insights from national and international standardisation bodies (e.g., International Standardisation Organisation (ISO), International Electrotechnical Committee (IEC), International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T)), identifying high-impact standards and gaps relevant to urban climate neutrality and smart city implementation.
- ▶ **Case Study Analysis:** Cities such as Aarhus, Aalborg, Kranj, Limassol, Turin, and Padua provide real-world examples of digital transformation aligned with green goals. Furthermore, illustrating challenges and opportunities in scaling local innovations through standards.
- ▶ **Policy and Standards Mapping:** The group conducts an in-depth mapping of European policy instruments (e.g., Climate City Contracts (CCC), Local Green Deals (LGD)) against existing standards, identifying opportunities for alignment with frameworks such as ISO 37101, DIN SPEC 91607, and ITU-T Y.4900-series.
- ▶ **Recommendations for Action:** A set of six strategic recommendation pillars is developed, addressing: Standards as Policy Instruments
 1. Localisation, Practicality and Capacity Building
 2. Stakeholder Collaboration and Inclusion
 3. Bridging research and innovation with standards
 4. Digital Infrastructure and Smart Public Services
 5. International alignment and leadership

■ Strategic Recommendations and Next Steps

The group advocates that standards be used not only as technical instruments but also as **strategic enablers** for policy implementation, ensuring continuity, scalability, and interoperability across diverse governance contexts, thereby optimising the appropriation and implementation of the “sustainable and smart” approach. To that end, it proposes, among others:

- ▶ The creation of a new Working Group under CEN/TC 465 on climate-neutral and smart cities.
- ▶ A revised business plan emphasising local digital twins and AI in the context of cities and communities, and energy-positive districts.
- ▶ Strengthening the collaboration with European Commission initiatives and international Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs).

- ▷ Formal integration of case study-derived blueprints and project outputs into the standardisation pipeline via CEN Workshop Agreements (CWAs), new work items, and harmonised specifications.
- ▷ Advocating for a better inclusion of cities and communities in standardisation through novel stakeholder engagement approaches.
- ▷ Position relevant national work on the European level.

This report marks a significant milestone in bridging the gap between local stakeholders, innovation and standardisation for the sustainable development of Europe's cities and communities. It showcases the potential of standards to catalyse Europe's twin transition, translating local experimentation into institutionalised transformation. The group's work calls for continued coordination, strategic leadership, and dedicated resources to ensure that Europe's cities remain at the forefront of smart, inclusive, and climate-neutral development. Standardisation is a collaborative effort – the work of the Ad hoc Group underscored this point, and we sincerely thank all contributors.

■ Recommendations

The recommendations should serve as an orientation for future standardisation work. They outline key findings from the exchange between members of CEN/TC 465, representing key European initiatives, and representatives from European organisations, cities, and communities. The recommendations are structured into six main action fields spanning from the institutional to the implementation level. The recommendations are addressed to experts, incl. cities and communities, European standardisation committees, and the European Commission.

1. Standards as Strategic Policy Instruments

- ▶ **Promote standards as policy enablers:** Enhance the strategic use of standardisation within major EU frameworks, such as the Green Deal, Clean Industrial Deal, and the Cities Mission, to ensure widespread, low-overhead implementation, continuity, and enforceability.
- ▶ **Support long-term legacy and scaling:** Utilise standards as an enabler to sustain the outcomes of temporary projects and foster transferability across countries, regions, cities, and communities.
- ▶ **Ensure longevity through strategic resourcing:** Strengthen the link between the European Annual Work Programme for Standardisation (AUWP) and the Rolling Plan for ICT Standards through appropriate strategic funding, including long-term planning, such as the timing of standard development and budget cycles at both local and regional levels.
- ▶ **Differentiate functional levels:** Standards should clearly distinguish between strategies, programmes, projects, and services to support appropriate uptake and evaluation, taking into account budgeting cycles and procurement processes.
- ▶ **Holistic view on data:** Recognise and promote data standards as an essential instrument for decision-support, management, as well as technical implementations, such as trusted data transactions and data spaces.

2. Localisation, Practicality, and Capability Building

- ▶ **Tailor standards for local and regional governments (LRGs):** Recognise the economic power and diversity of LRGs by creating adaptable standards that fit various sizes and capacities. By strengthening their involvement in the standardisation process, we ensure that the resulting standards are not only technically sound but also socially relevant and fit for purpose.
- ▶ **Design and promote shared solutions:** Interoperable and modular solutions allow replication across territories. Within a framework of open innovation, this spans technical, methodological, and legal conditions, extending beyond data to include instruments and services.
- ▶ **Simplify procurement and implementation:** Local knowledge is essential for identifying practical needs and streamlining resources, enabling standards that deliver real value and promote efficiency. Design standards to reduce complexity for Local & Regional Governments (LRGs), enabling smoother policy delivery and reducing administrative burdens. Develop standards that make them a valuable resource to support public procurement in LRG.
- ▶ **Empower through training and tools:** Provide public administrators with learning resources and instruments to understand, apply, and shape standards.

3. Stakeholder Collaboration and Inclusion

- ▶ **Endorse and enable multi-level and horizontal integration:** Standardise collaboration mechanisms across government levels (vertical) and beyond silos (horizontal) to support co-creation and co-ownership of standards. Creating appropriate instruments for the integration.
- ▶ **Engage citizens and underrepresented groups:** Integrate participatory approaches into standard-setting processes, especially in energy transition and smart service standards, which allow underrepresented groups to voice their needs and become recognised as experts in their own right.

- ▶ **Strengthen the public sector's role in standardisation:** Enhance LRG representation in SDOs by providing funding options and simplified pathways (e.g., guest status) for participation and collaboration. Establish new models of engagement, such as dedicated city clusters or observer roles tailored to public authorities, to enhance collaboration and effectiveness.

4. Better Bridging Between Research & Innovation Actions and Standardisation

- ▶ **Utilise cities as living labs:** Ensure that cities involved in R&I projects participate in, test, and provide feedback on standards development to promote relevance and scalability. Drawing inspiration from the many successful local initiatives and instruments explored by this group, including the work carried out by Mission Cities, Local Green Deals to accelerate systemic action implementation, pilots in Data Spaces for Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities, and the Local Digital Twin toolbox.
- ▶ **Establish structured transfer mechanisms:** Create comprehensive instruments that systematise integrating EU project outputs into the respective technical committees and recognised and tested standards.
- ▶ **Evolve CWAs into long-term standards:** Move beyond isolated CWAs toward a holistic, Europe-wide standardisation framework based on project learning using, e.g. well-established European expert platforms.
- ▶ **Overcome disconnect:** Standards development processes and public funding and sponsorships are misaligned, hindering a successful positioning of R&I output.

5. Digital Infrastructure and Smart Public Services

- ▶ **Develop integrated standards for Data Spaces, Digital Twins, and CitiVerse:** Align with ongoing European initiatives. Ensure that AI applications are designed and deployed in accordance with ethical, transparent, and accountable standards that promote fairness, inclusivity, and environmental sustainability.
- ▶ **Standardise data and indicators:** Promote open standards for data collection, access, and sharing, as well as for AI model transparency and accountability. Develop consistent metrics for assessing the impact of the twin transition, including co-benefits across sectors such as energy, mobility, and public health.
- ▶ **Leverage digital for transparency and trust:** Embed digital solutions in service delivery standards to enhance accountability in key areas of public interest, underpinned by robust frameworks of trust and security, ensuring integrity, privacy, and resilience across all platforms. Prioritise trustworthiness in AI through robust governance frameworks that ensure data integrity, privacy, cybersecurity, and algorithmic accountability. This is essential for fostering citizen confidence and safeguarding democratic values during the digital transformation of cities and communities.

6. International Alignment and Leadership

- ▶ **Position EU priorities globally:** Align European standards with ISO/IEC and ITU-T developments, and vice versa, to work towards global standards that are relevant to the EU and are in line with European values. Leverage the results of the ad hoc Group on the international level in the newly established JCT 4 Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities.
- ▶ **Fragmentation on the international level:** Overcoming the current fragmentation, appealing to the new JCT 4 leadership for a concise approach for future international standards.
- ▶ **EU leadership through national recognition:** Recognising and integrating the work done by national experts by integrating well-established publicly available specifications (PAS) into the work programme of CEN/TC 465 or other relevant mirror committee.
- ▶ **Input case studies and project outcomes into international efforts:** Encourage EU-funded projects and initiatives to contribute to global standardisation processes, ensuring harmonisation and enhancing Europe's influence. Strengthen Europe's global leadership by aligning strategic innovation with on-the-ground implementation.

■ Proposed Immediate Actions for CEN/TC 465

Based on the recommendations, six concrete actions are proposed to CEN/TC 465.

A1. Leadership & Governance

- ▷ Strengthen the leadership position of CEN/TC 465 on governance and holistic approaches for sustainable and smart city development.
- ▷ Propose the establishment of a new Working Group on climate-neutral and smart cities, building on the foundation laid by the Ad Hoc Group.
- ▷ Promote recurring engagement with key stakeholders and initiatives, following in the steps of the former Sector Forum.

A2. Integration & Alignment

- ▷ Integrate findings from the Ad Hoc Group into CEN/CLC JTC 4 and ITU-T Study Group 20.
- ▷ Strategically align relevant European projects with the work of JTC 4 and ITU-T.
- ▷ Foster strong collaboration with relevant TC on the European level, such as CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 and with committees on digital twin within ETSI.

A3. Business Plan Revision

- ▷ Focus the revision of the CEN/TC 465 business plan on key areas such as thematic and integrated Local Digital Twins (LDTs), Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) as an implementation instrument for climate-neutral and smart cities, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in service to the transformation of cities and communities.
- ▷ Encourage national mirror committees to flag relevant PASs and CWAs for consideration and integration into the business plan.

A4. Standardisation Pipeline

- ▷ Promote the elevation of relevant national standards published (e.g., DIN SPEC 91637 *Impact measurement of municipal climate actions* and DIN SPEC 91607 *Digital twins for cities and municipalities*) or under development (CYS) to shape the twin transition on the European level.
- ▷ Ensure future standards align with the budgeting and procurement cycles of local and regional governments.
- ▷ Track upcoming CWAs related to climate-neutral and smart cities and capture their outcomes in the form of New Work Items.

A5. Liaison & Project Engagement

- ▷ Actively encourage liaisons with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives such as the Data Space Support Centre.
- ▷ Feed the outcomes of the Ad Hoc Group into the commencing work of ISO/IEC JTC 4 as a European contribution.
- ▷ Advocate for a dedicated EISMEA Action Grant to pilot procurement based on relevant standards.

A6. Framework Development

- ▷ Develop a coordination framework similar to the Sector Forum model to support the ongoing engagement of the research community and provide strategic oversight regarding relevant developments at the European level.
- ▷ Establish new models of engagement, remote participation, dedicated city clusters, or observer roles tailored to public authorities in collaboration with CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC).

■ Introduction

Europe has identified the green and digital transition, often referred to as the twin transition, as a core area for its economic development. Existing or past projects aimed at implementing intelligent, climate-neutral cities, however, suggest that there is a pressing need for better integration between individual European initiatives and projects (European Court of Auditors, 2023), as well as for improved integration between green/climate and digital solutions. These findings highlight the significance of the work in CEN/TC 465 and underscore the need for clarity on potential pathways forward.

In this canon, the European Standardisation Strategy is a key policy document. The European Standardisation Strategy is a key supporter of a more resilient, greener, and smarter Europe, backing the CEN-CENELEC Strategy 2030. Underscoring the role of a twin transition for Europe's economy, environment, and society, the strategy provides a solid foundation for our work. In support of the implementation of the EU Standardisation Strategy in 2023, the European High-Level Forum on European Standardisation (hereinafter referred to as HLF) was established. The annual work programme saw the topic "cities" integrated into workstream 8¹. W58 concluded its work laying out strategic orientations for future work. The published recommendations, targeting a strategic level, guide future topics relevant to standardisation in cities and communities. However, it is worth noting that cities and communities had no continuous representation in the HLF. Further, the translation of the recommendations will require a deep integration with the Mission Platform and the various projects under the Digital Europe Programme. This, however, falls outside the mandate of the HLF and needs to be "owned" by the respective standard-developing organisations and their technical committees.

Building on the recommendations, the work of the Ad-hoc group holds significant promise in bridging the gap between strategic considerations and the recognition of the needs of cities and communities. The participation and interest expressed by liaison projects and Local and Regional Governments (hereinafter referred to as LRGs) underscore the importance of rethinking stakeholder engagement in orchestrating the transformation of our cities and communities. The Ad hoc Group's ability to integrate state-of-the-art knowledge in cities and communities across Europe paves the way to advance an integrated and efficient approach to smart city development.

■ Expected Impact

The joint initiative proposed by DIN and DS to the CEN/TC 465 will enhance the understanding and knowledge base for standards supporting the EU's "100 climate-neutral and smart cities" mission and purpose-driven ICT standardisation, specifically through the Ad Hoc Group "Climate-Neutral Smart Cities and Communities" in CEN/TC 465. The Ad hoc Group aims to build and consolidate synergies with existing European initiatives, programs, and platforms focused on advancing climate-neutral and smart cities.

We aim to put cities and communities, their knowledge, and learning, at the centre of this work. They cover a wide range of topics in their daily work, spanning from IoT to data platforms and digital twins, to leveraging advanced technologies such as blockchain, machine learning, and earth observation in their journey towards climate neutrality.

Through open and collaborative engagement with relevant stakeholders, the Ad hoc Group aims to deepen the understanding of cities and communities within CEN/TC 465 and raise awareness of their critical role in the twin transition. This multi-stakeholder approach results in the drafting of initial recommendations for further standardisation within CEN/TC 465 or other relevant technical committees. These recommendations lay the foundation for a future Technical Report (TR) in CEN/TC 465, potentially leading to the development of a comprehensive standardisation roadmap in the space of climate-neutral and smart cities. This future roadmap will contribute to the ICT Rolling Plan, supporting the twin transition of European cities.

The strategy aims to promote and develop a European vision for smart cities, characterised by inclusivity, democracy, and sustainability, through the process of standardisation. The document includes targeted recommendations for relevant stakeholders and offers a comprehensive overview of the European organisations and programmes that support urban development. Final report [here](#).

To further these objectives, the Ad hoc Group aims to:

- ▷ Establish a robust European knowledge base that facilitates the creation of future standards at both European and international levels.
- ▷ Raise awareness of existing outcomes and ongoing initiatives that support the green and digital transformation within CEN/TC 465.
- ▷ Encourage key initiatives, such as the NetZeroCities project consortium, to integrate standards as a fundamental policy instrument in their ongoing and future work on the twin transition.
- ▷ Recognise and amplify the contributions of European cities and communities to advance the twin transition, showcasing their efforts and best practices to a broader audience.
- ▷ Attract new stakeholders from diverse sectors, including cities, industry, and research, to actively contribute to standardisation activities relating to the local and regional levels.
- ▷ Signal to the standardisation community the need to prepare for future standardisation efforts, setting the stage for coordinated and impactful action.

■ Operational Mode

The Ad hoc Group comprises CEN/TC 465 members and interested parties, maintaining regular liaison with the relevant technical committee to ensure alignment and integration with ongoing work. Guest speakers are continually invited to contribute to the knowledge base. The operational approach is based on principles of openness, transparency, and agility, ensuring broad participation and shared ownership throughout the process.

Openness and Inclusivity:

- ▷ The Ad hoc Group operates openly and flexibly, enabling broad stakeholder engagement. This approach allows for active participation from all interested parties, including CEN/TC 465 members and external experts.
- ▷ Monthly online meetings are scheduled, offering a consistent opportunity for members and invited guests to participate, ensuring continuous engagement and commitment from all involved parties.

Agile and Collaborative Process:

- ▷ The format of the Ad hoc Group enables an agile and adaptive working process, which is less constrained by formal or bureaucratic working group procedures. This flexibility allows the group to quickly adapt to new insights, opportunities, or challenges and effectively engage with stakeholders.
- ▷ Weekly calls between the co-convenors will ensure that the group remains responsive and can adjust the process based on evolving needs or external developments. This enables effective coordination, preparation, and real-time decision-making.

Inclusive Contribution and Shared Ownership:

- ▷ The group fosters inclusive and shared ownership of the work. Contributions will be divided based on expertise and capacity, ensuring that every member is actively involved in the drafting and review processes.
- ▷ The writing process is collaborative, with contributions from all members of the Ad hoc Group. This ensures that the resulting recommendations are comprehensive, representative, and reflective of the diverse perspectives within the group.
- ▷ A Recommendation Committee is established to draft the final recommendations jointly, ensuring that different voices and perceptions are heard. The Committee includes representatives from various countries and stakeholders.

Public Accessibility and Final Publication:

- ▶ The final report produced by the Ad hoc Group is publicly available in open online repositories, ensuring that the outcomes of the group's work are accessible to the broader community, stakeholders, and the public. This promotes knowledge sharing and facilitates broader engagement with the resulting standards and recommendations.

■ Policy framework

The following section gives insights into key policy frameworks that support the aim of the Ad hoc Group. For several years, standardisation has become the implementation arm of European policy-making.

The **European Green Deal** establishes the overarching policy vision for transforming the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy, aiming to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. It seeks to decouple economic growth from resource use while ensuring that no person or place is left behind. Operationalised through an extensive suite of strategies, laws, and funding programmes, the Green Deal builds the foundation of the CEN/TC 465 business plan. During Von der Leyen's recent term, the **Clean Industrial Deal** succeeded the Green Deal.

The twin green and digital transition, which is formalised in the **Declaration on a Green and Digital Transformation**, was signed by all 27 EU Member States. This declaration acknowledges the potential of digitalisation to support environmental goals and commits Member States to adopt enabling technologies, including digital twins, for climate monitoring and urban management. It builds on the EU's strategic communication *Shaping Europe's Digital Future*, emphasising inclusion, fairness, and sustainability, positioning Europe as a global leader in responsible digital development.

The **Digital Decade Policy Programme (2021–2030)** outlines Europe's digital ambitions for the coming decade. It provides a governance framework to coordinate digital transformation efforts across Member States, with clear targets for digital skills, infrastructure, digitalisation of public services, and business uptake of advanced technologies. The programme is implemented through a range of instruments, most notably the **Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)**.

The **Digital Europe Programme**, with a budget of €7.5 billion (2021–2027), funds strategic investments in key digital capacities, including supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills, and the widespread adoption of digital technologies. The first work programme (2021–2022) introduced the concept of data spaces for smart communities and initiated foundational work on the **Local Digital Twin (LDT) Toolbox**. The second work programme (2023–2024) builds on this by integrating forward-looking concepts such as the **CitiVerse**, a European virtual world ecosystem where LDTs connect citizens, governments, and services through immersive technologies like AR/VR.

Digitalisation relies on robust legal and ethical frameworks. The EU has developed a comprehensive suite of legislation to ensure data protection, interoperability, cybersecurity, and the responsible use of technology. Key regulations include:

- ▶ **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016)**: Ensures that all personal data collected, processed, or stored by LDTs respects individuals' privacy rights, including consent, purpose limitation, and data minimisation.
- ▶ **Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868)**: Facilitates trusted data sharing across sectors and borders, establishing safeguards and governance models to support voluntary exchanges.
- ▶ **Data Act (adopted 2024)**: Expands access to industrial and IoT data, clarifies the rights and obligations of users, providers, and intermediaries, and paves the way for fair and transparent data use in systems such as digital twins.
- ▶ **Open Data Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/1024)**: Encourages the reuse of public sector information and supports open government data practices, which are core to LDT deployment.
- ▶ **INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC)**: Mandates harmonisation and interoperability of spatial data infrastructures, which are fundamental for geospatially enabled LDTs.
- ▶ **NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555)**: Strengthens cybersecurity across essential digital infrastructures, including smart city systems.
- ▶ **ePrivacy Directive (2002/58/EC)**: Addresses confidentiality of communications and applies to digital twin components that rely on electronic communications data.
- ▶ **European Strategy for Data**: Sets out a vision for a single EU data market based on sovereignty, transparency, and innovation, which underpins most digital twin-related policies.

Other notable legislation includes the **Digital Services Act (DSA)** and the **Digital Markets Act (DMA)**, both adopted in 2022, which govern platform behaviour, data governance, and fair competition. The **Artificial Intelligence Act**, now in its final stages of adoption, will create a horizontal regulatory framework for trustworthy AI, with implications for AI-enabled LDTs and digital governance tools.

The **Interoperable Europe Act**, proposed in 2023, aims to set common standards and processes for digital public services across Member States. This act prompts shared specifications and cross-border compatibility, central to building a European ecosystem of smart, sustainable cities.

The rapid decarbonisation of mobility, the building stock, and the urban energy system is outlined in the **European Law on Climate (2021/1119)**. It sets an ambitious goal for limiting emissions by 2030, increasing the reduction percentage from the initial 40% to 55% compared to 1990 values. “Clean Energy for All Europeans” is the legal framework for achieving the EU’s climate objectives, encompassing a series of regulations aimed at decarbonising the EU’s energy system. The **Mission for 100 Climate-neutral and Smart Cities** ties into these objectives.

Existing Standards and related initiatives

The following section presents results obtained from screening international, European and national standards for their relevance. The standards often do not explicitly reference climate targets or decarbonisation. A ranking was included to help the readers navigate. Only resources with a high or medium relevance are included. Furthermore, the list is a snapshot of the existing overall landscape and may not capture all standards. The overview focuses on standards situated at the intersection of climate neutrality and digitalisation. The overview aims not to repeat the work conducted in the HLF WS8 but to complement it. Further, the work in CEN/TC 465 did not include structured considerations of “Smart Cities” or digitalisation. The overview will thus serve as a first knowledge base. The central part of the work was conducted in May 2025, with minor updates included in September 2025.

International level

A primary reference is the collection of standards collected by the [IEC-ISO-ITU Joint Smart Cities Task Force](#) (J-SCTF). It is available in both [interactive graphic](#) and spreadsheet formats.

The following provides an overview of the most relevant standards identified by the international standards developing organisations ISO, IEC, and ITU-T (United Nations). The list may not be exhaustive and is subject to ongoing evaluation.

ITU-T Standards

ITU is the UN specialised agency for information and communication technologies (ICTs). The work presented below is part of the work programme of ITU T Study Group 20. The study group is responsible for developing innovative standards (ITU-T Recommendations), guidelines, reports, methodologies, and best practices for the Internet of Things (IoT), digital twins, the metaverse, and smart sustainable cities and communities (SSC&C), to accelerate digital transformation in both urban and rural areas.

Standard	Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
ITU-T Y.4600 (2022)	Digital twins for smart cities	High	Critical for modelling decarbonisation , emissions tracking, and systemic urban planning.
ITU-T Y.4122 (2021)	Edge-computing-enabled IoT gateway	Medium	Technical enabler; indirectly supports smart energy and mobility services.
ITU-T Y.4200–4201	Smart city platforms & interoperability	High	Relevant for integrating decentralised climate solutions (e.g. solar, e-mobility).
ITU-T Y.4900–4909	KPIs and assessment for SSCs	High	Core to monitoring and evaluating progress toward climate neutrality.
ITU-T Y.4903 (2016)	KPIs for SDG alignment	High	Could align well with Climate City Contracts if contextualised to EU priorities.
ITU-T Y.4904/4905	Maturity models, impact assessment	High	These models could underpin city benchmarking frameworks under Horizon outputs.

Standard	Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
ITU-T Y.4461 (2020)	Open data in smart cities	High	Foundational for interoperability, transparency , and shared climate indicators.
ITU-T Y.4470 (2020)	AI service exposure architecture	Medium	AI can enable predictive modelling, but it needs stronger climate-related use cases .
ITU-T Y.4472 (2020)	APIs for IoT data	Medium	Could help standardise data from diverse urban decarbonisation platforms .
ITU-T Y.4556/4561/4562	Smart residential communities, blockchain	Medium	Enable local sustainability data management, but not focused on climate neutrality .

Even though the newly agreed ITU-T Y.4505 has not yet been included in the collection of standards collected by the [IEC-ISO-ITU Joint Smart Cities Task Force](#) (J-SCTF)

ITU-T Y.4505	Minimal interoperability mechanisms for smart and sustainable cities and communities	High	Provides a structure and process for the development of Minimal interoperability Mechanisms supporting the integration of data from different sources to inform the better management.
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IEC Standards and Initiatives

The committee under scrutiny is the IEC System Committee Smart City. **IEC SyC Smart City** promotes the development of standards in electrotechnology to enhance the integration, interoperability, and effectiveness of city systems. In particular, the initiative on **Positive Energy Districts** is outlined in more detail below.

IEC SyC Smart Cities - Positive Energy Districts ahG 17

The ahG 17 aims to focus on the topic of Positive Energy Districts. The ahG 17 seeks to establish a common framework for cities to collaborate and learn from one another. While PED is becoming an increasingly common approach among cities to tackle the climate crisis, specialist technical standards committees have not yet approached the topic. The AHG 17 thus raises the importance of this topic and supports an ongoing collaborative approach to delivering the necessary standards.

The findings will be summarised in a **Technology Report on PEDs**, which will be built collaboratively with all working groups within IEC SyC Smart Cities. This report will provide a common foundation to enable those working groups to develop deliverables consistently. The recommendations will include proposing further preliminary work, such as a PWI (for example, *“Positive Energy Districts (PED) deliverable roadmaps”*). The work might be integrated into the upcoming JTC 4.

Standard	Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
IEC 63152:2020	City service continuity – role of electrical supply	High	Addresses resilience of electricity, a core pillar of climate-neutral energy systems.
IEC SRD 63152-2:2022	Guidelines on service continuity	Medium	Emphasises continuity planning , relevant for climate adaptation and resilience.
IEC SRD 63188:2022	Smart Cities Reference Architecture Methodology	High	Could be foundational for integrating climate KPIs into digital platforms.
IEC SRD 63235:2021	Concept methodology for smart cities	Medium-High	Could support the standardisation of climate action planning methods .
IEC SRD 63273-1/2	City Information Modelling (CIM)	High	CIM basis to simulate climate scenarios, emissions, and infrastructure adaptation.
IEC SRD 63301-1	Water systems in smart cities	Medium-Low	Water is key to resilience. To date, the topic of water is underrepresented in CEN/TC 465.
IEC SRD 63320-1	Urban planning for smart cities	High	Directly relevant to decarbonised mobility and buildings , but needs integration with EU missions.
IEC SRD 63476-1	Gap analysis for smart city ontology	Medium	Linked to IEC Tech Report: Ontology (2023)
IEC SRD 63520:2024	Energy challenge and concept system building	High	Highly relevant to climate-neutral energy systems . Needs aligning with EU-specific goals under the Mission and policy targets.
IEC Tech Report: City Info Modelling (CIM, 2021)	Digital twins and CIM	High	Support city-scale simulations , e.g. supporting decision-making support instruments.
IEC Tech Report: Ontology (2023)	Ontologies in smart cities	Medium	Useful for interoperability , but still abstract, would benefit from concrete KPIs or use cases.

Due to the topical alignment and existing liaison, the focus is **on ISO/TC 268 Sustainable Cities and Communities** and its **subcommittees**. ISO/TC 268 includes developing requirements, frameworks, guidance, and supporting techniques and tools related to achieving sustainable development. Its subcommittees focus on smart infrastructure and smart mobility & transportation, respectively.

Standard	Title / Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
ISO 37101	Sustainable development in communities – Management system	High	Can serve as a core framework for vertical integration of policies, LDTs, and PEDs. Foundational to the EU Cities Mission, ICC, NZC, LGDs
ISO 37120	Indicators for city services and quality of life	High	Ties directly into monitoring and evaluation under the Green Deal and CCCs
ISO 37122	Indicators for smart cities	High	Supports smart governance , benchmarking, digital public services. May lack a clear integration of metrics relevant to the European frameworks.
ISO 37123	Indicators for resilient cities	Medium–High	Tied to climate adaptation strategies under EU Climate Law, but possibly underrepresented in the discussion around the EU Missions.
ISO 37106	Guidance on establishing smart city operating models	Medium	Valuable guide for LDT deployment and integration into city operations
ISO 23386 / 23387	Terminology and data templates for construction and digital twins	High	Relevant for built environment digitalisation projects, particularly technical implementation such as PED or CitiVerse
ISO/IEC 30182	Smart city concept model – a shared data ontology	High	Supports semantic interoperability critical for LDT Toolbox and EU Data Strategy , but requires harmonisation with existing work such as UNE standards and DIN SPEC 91607

European level

The following highlights European standards developed as [CEN Workshop Agreements](#) that are of relevance for future considerations.

Standard	Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
CWA 17382	Sustainable Energy Retrofit Process Management for Multi-Occupancy Residential Buildings with Owner Communities	High	Structured the information collection and workflow , resulting in thoroughly analysed energy retrofit options , recognising the different interests and priorities of the owner community.
CWA 17381	The Description and Assessment of Good Practices for Smart City Solutions	High	Guidance in describing good practices for all types of smart city solutions .
CWA 18125	Trusted Data Transaction	Medium-High	Guidance that provides terminology, concepts and mechanisms in the field of data exchange, focusing on trusted data transactions.
CWA 18245	Trusted Data Transaction - Part 2: Trustworthiness requirements	Medium-High	Guidance defines a set of foundational principles for trusted data transactions , establishes general requirements and detailed requirements for each phase.

National level

The following highlights national standards developed either as a PAS or a full standard.

Standard	Focus	Relevance to Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities	Observations
DIN SPEC 91637	Impact measurement for municipal, regional, and national climate protection	High	Supports evidence-based climate planning linking to ISO 37101 on performance & improvement and ISO 37120 on indicators for quality of life.
<u>DIN SPEC 91627</u>	Greenhouse gas emissions accounting for municipalities	High	Core to climate neutrality tracking , relevant to the EU Cities Mission and NZC .
<u>DIN SPEC 91607</u>	Digital twins for cities and municipalities	High	Directly supports LDT development , includes maturity models and use cases. Relevant to EDIC, CitiVerse, and Digital Europe Programme .
<u>UNI 11965:2024</u>	Stakeholder involvement in local governance	High	Aligns with ISO 37101's participatory governance principles. Bridges policy, planning, and citizen engagement.
<u>UNI 11973:2025</u>	Building lifecycle integration with city-level sustainability	Medium–High	Adds a valuable link between building-level and city-level sustainability, supports systems thinking.
UNE 178201:2016	Smart city definitions and key attributes	High	Provides a baseline taxonomy and classification aligned with broader smart city strategies .
UNE 178202:2016	Urban indicators and dashboards	High	Facilitates monitoring and evaluation ; could be linked to ITU-T Y.4900-series .
UNE 178104:2017	Interoperability for smart city platforms	High	Supports digital twin and platform integration , highly aligned with EU digital policy goals.
UNE 178301:2015	Open data for citizen engagement	Medium–High	Enables transparency and participation , essential for trust and effective governance.

■ Case Studies

Growing attention on Smart Cities and Communities has led to significant activity at the European level, supported by various funding streams and institutions. These efforts have created a critical mass of solutions and outputs that advance the twin transition. Many European cities and communities co-designed these solutions while serving as testing grounds. However, many of the solutions developed so far remain closely tied to specific programmes and funding opportunities. Against this backdrop, the Ad hoc Group aims to identify relevant initiatives and outputs that can inform and guide the standardisation process. The local cases and initiatives integrate the following points:

- ▶ **Scalability & Replicability:** The case is not one-off or niche initiatives, but offers scalable and replicable solutions that can be implemented across various European cities and contexts, utilising mainstream financial instruments. Ideally developed and tested through a consortium and in multiple cities or settings.
- ▶ **Green & Digital Transformation:** Highlighting how digital technologies are leveraged to advance green and sustainable urban development, the case aligns with climate action and the goals of the EU's Digital Decade.
- ▶ **Integrated Approach:** Demonstrating a cross-departmental and cross-sectoral strategy, the case integrates various municipal sectors and stakeholders to achieve climate-neutrality objectives.
- ▶ **Target Emission Domains:** The case focuses on linking digitalisation with at least one of the following domains: green industry, mobility and transport, circular economy, nature-based solutions, built environment, or energy systems.
- ▶ **Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration:** Outlining the successful engagement of multiple stakeholders, including public and private, local and regional, the case demonstrates a holistic approach to meeting objectives.
- ▶ **Proven Results & Flexibility:** Adaptability was tested, refined, and proven effective in various urban environments and conditions.
- ▶ **Balanced approach:** While achieving specific sustainability targets, the case recognises social and economic viability in diverse communities, including urban, rural, and other types of geographical and demographic diversity.

This call opened for four months (winter period 2025-2026) to municipalities, municipal-controlled utilities, communities, and companies across Europe. We aim for a geographical, topical, and technological spread across Europe. Due to the overwhelming response, we adapted our general approach, including one additional meeting and extending the meeting duration. In the following section, cases in regional and local governments will be presented, outlining the approaches implemented, findings, and further needs that have been identified.

■ Case Studies of Regional and Local Governments

To support the work, the needs and realities of the regional and local governments are investigated through presentations by several cities across Europe.

Aarhus, Denmark

The municipal agency Innovation, Technology, and Creativity (ITK) in the City of Aarhus, a mission-driven city, leads several initiatives that combine ICT and data-driven approaches across various sectors, including climate adaptation, business innovation, and urban livability. To support sustainable digital transformation, ITK promotes interoperability, open-source solutions, standardisation, data innovation, citizen engagement, and transparent digital governance.

An example of the twin transition in action is the **city's IoT infrastructure**, built on a self-governed, FIWARE-compliant platform. This enables **interoperability** with diverse IoT providers, including digital twin suppliers. While **technical deployment and scaling** (e.g., data spaces) are straightforward, challenges persist in **organisational culture and structure** - including internal **silos, limited collaboration** with R&D partners, and varying competence levels, which hinder innovation and uptake.

Aalborg, Denmark

The City of Aalborg has successfully implemented **Local Green Deals (LGDs) to engage local companies** in its **decarbonisation** journey. Through the Aalborg Climate Alliance, companies are selected based on their potential for CO₂ reduction and existing climate commitments. With 83 LGDs in place, the partnerships involve mutual obligations for **holistic climate action, encompassing direct decarbonisation efforts, supply chain engagement, and public climate ambassadorship**. This approach reflects a **systemic and replicable model** of collaborative sustainability.

Cork, Ireland

Currently, the most significant redevelopment area in Ireland, Cork's Docklands, is set to become a new lively hub at the city's waterfront. Through an integrated approach to **public space, the built environment, and mobility**, the area will transition from an industrial zone to a mixed-use area, featuring residential, entertainment, and office spaces. The Docklands are an integral part of Cork's case study in the Horizon project TIPS4PED. The planning will thus integrate **digital instruments**, such as a **digital twin**, and aim to support Cork's climate targets as outlined in their Mission application.

Figure 1: Ceremony in Aalborg to welcome new climate partners to the Climate Alliance.

Kranj, Slovenia

Kranj is one of the early pilot cities in the DS4SSCC initiative on Data Spaces. Since 2019, the city has been developing a **sovereign data platform to support its climate and digital ambitions**. Key innovations include an integrated transport card (in partnership with VISA) and a blockchain-based NFT model for **service management**.

The city's Climate City Contract (CCC) is being translated into a concrete action and implementation plan by the Office of Development and Smart Communities. This ensures **alignment between digital innovation and climate neutrality**, creating a foundation for future standardisation, particularly around data governance and community-led integration.

Limassol, Cyprus

Geographical constraints, traffic congestion, and urban density have made climate adaptation a priority for Limassol. As a Mission City, it is addressing urban heat island effects through participatory approaches, stakeholder workshops, and urban fabric redesign. The city aims to position itself as a regional leader within the Mediterranean by **sharing findings and driving replication**.

With the support of the national government and the Cyprus Organisation for Standardisation (CYS), Limassol intends to launch a **national standard to scale instruments such as the Climate City Contract**. They plan to adapt the model for broader uptake of local climate governance mechanisms.

Tilliria Region, Cyprus

Tilliria region would be one of the uptake regions. Tilliria is developing a **climate-neutral regional strategy** that acknowledges its **geopolitical isolation, energy dependency, and financial and infrastructure limitations**. Beyond renewable energy and transport electrification, the initiative focuses on **sustainable tourism, the preservation of cultural heritage, and the protection of biodiversity**. By valuing traditional knowledge and ecological integrity, Tilliria reflects the need for a **place-based approach**, seeking to secure EU funding for the implementation of its long-term governance strategy.

Turin, Italy

Turin's Positive Energy District (PED) highlights the importance of **stakeholder engagement for replication**. Situated in a mixed-use area with residential buildings, university facilities, and municipal infrastructure, the PED is fed by the local thermal plant. To tie the local action to the broader context, the city implemented a comprehensive **citizen engagement strategy, which included stakeholder mapping, awareness campaigns, gamification, and co-creation workshops**. Citizens participated in measuring, discussing, and reviewing their energy consumption, contributing to shared visions for current and future energy needs. Turin's case underlines the importance of integrating **citizen feedback into standardisation** processes to ensure inclusivity and societal relevance.

Padua, Italy

Padova has pursued climate action for over 20 years, initially through the Covenant of Mayors. Participation in the EU Cities Mission shifted the focus to achieving climate neutrality by 2030, with actions backing away from the goal of Climate Neutrality. The city received the Mission Label in May 2025.

Figure 2: Historical Centre of the City of Padua.

While the Climate City Contract has been instrumental, Padova identifies a **lack of standardised management tools** for handling these contracts across different levels of government and stakeholder ecosystems. It also highlights the **need for guidance on replication** in citizen participation and co-creation. In particular, data management, covering flow, quality, access, and sharing, remains a challenge. Future standardisation in **data governance will be key to improving decision-making, monitoring, and communication** of climate action outcomes.

■ Relevant Initiatives

As a second important part of the work, the call for case studies extended to projects and initiatives. Still, the approach was more direct, utilising the rich network of the convenors and participants in the Ad hoc group. This reflected the objective of the Ad hoc Group to create and consolidate synergies with existing initiatives, programmes, and platforms at the European level in the space of “climate-neutral and smart cities.” In the first section, the report summarises findings on strategic high-level initiatives, while the second section summarises work in specific projects, platforms and initiatives.

Strategic initiatives by the European Commission

The [Work Stream 8 Report](#), endorsed by the High-Level Forum for European Standardisation (HLF), underlines the need for strategic prioritisation of **standardisation of sustainable and smart cities and communities**. Doing so would not only enhance the implementation of European policies for sustainable development but also reinforce Europe’s international influence, particularly through mechanisms such as the **Vienna Agreement framework**. Among its key proposals is a call to enshrine pivotal urban-related standards in the **Annual Union Work Programme on European Standardisation (AUWP)**. The report advocates for a standardisation request for **Local Digital Twins (LDTs)** to be included in AUWP 2025, with further requests in 2026 focusing on climate mitigation, carbon neutrality, climate adaptation, and urban resilience. The standardisation of local digital twins aligns with ongoing initiatives under the Digital Europe Programme (see below). The aim is to support the rollout of smart city services, informing sustainability indicators, and integrating these digital tools into city governance frameworks. Additionally, to position Europe better in the international ICT market.

Several initiatives by the EC support the ambition, one of which is [StandICT.eu 2026](#). **StandICT.eu 2026** supports European experts engaged in standardisation activities across various topics. Building on the success of two previous editions, the current programme offers not only seed funding but also runs a dedicated observatory and academy. These tools help track emerging trends, disseminate knowledge, and provide entry points for both newcomers and experienced professionals.

Standardisation and policy integration

The ad hoc group references the **EU Mission, “100 climate-neutral and smart cities”** (also known as the Cities Mission), which sparked interest at both the European and international levels. The EU Cities Mission was represented by **NetZeroCities**. The project and its wider ecosystems effectively develop key references for standards on smart and climate-neutral cities by bringing a common approach to transitioning towards climate neutrality in cities. These include the Climate City Contracts as an instrument for stakeholder integration, a transition map to orchestrate the transformation and monitoring advice. **Mission cities** are being encouraged to engage directly in the activities of CEN/TC 465, with cities like Kranj, Aarhus, Munich, and Limassol already contributing to the development and application of relevant standards. This active participation strengthens local governance capacities and ensures that future standards reflect on-the-ground realities, promoting scalability and long-term impact.

NetworkNature serves as the European platform for the Nature-based Solutions (NbS) community. Created by the European Commission, it brings together stakeholders from local, regional, and international levels to maximise the impact and spread of Nature-based Solutions. Complementing these efforts are more than 85 Horizon Europe projects. One is **GoNature Positive (GoNP!)**, an initiative advancing the concept of a Nature-Positive Economy. By addressing the interconnected crises of biodiversity loss and climate change, **GoNP!** aims to drive prosperity through green innovation, sustainable jobs, and food security. The project has brought together over 750 stakeholders from more than 50 countries to develop a shared foundation for future action. Its priorities include managing trade-offs between nature-positive and nature-negative impacts, integrating Indigenous knowledge,

and enhancing accountability. The initiative recognises standardisation bodies as crucial actors in this transition.

At the operational level, the **Smart Communities Network** is working to scale key digital tools, including **Local Digital Twins** and **Lordimas**, a maturity assessment tool. Supported by the European Commission and linked to the **Digital Europe Programme**, the network is a forum for cities with varying levels of digital readiness. One key output is a comprehensive set of [procurement guidelines and templates](#) for acquiring open, interoperable digital twin technologies. These materials, aligned with **EU Directives 24 and 25 (2024)** and the **MIMPlus** and **EIF4SCC** principles, ensure that cities can navigate the procurement process with confidence, from needs assessment to integrating environmental and social sustainability into tenders. The current phase includes the development of building blocks and a **standardisation roadmap for LDT and CitiVerse**.

All of these developments shall be continued and maintained by the **European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)** on Local Digital Twins and CitiVerse. In this next-generation virtual environment, city officials, citizens, and communities can interact using augmented and virtual reality. The CitiVerse promises to revolutionise participatory decision-making, allowing residents to explore urban planning projects, engage in virtual consultations, and co-design solutions to challenges such as traffic congestion and pollution. By creating a structured governance and technical framework for digital twin use across cities, the EDIC initiative lays the groundwork for the EU's long-term digital urban vision.

The **Intelligent Cities Challenge (ICC)** concluded in 2025 under the direction of DG GROW. ICC provided capacity-building support to over 200 European cities, helping them align their green and digital transitions through structured collaboration and **Local Green Deals (LGDs)**. These **LGDs** were co-developed by cities and local businesses and supported by a tailored [LGD Methodology](#), which is currently undergoing revision. By May 2025, the ICC had facilitated the creation of **207 LGDs** in various sectors, spanning from mobility, energy, construction, tourism, and culture. While many of these agreements are still in early stages, a significant share (around 40%) has already demonstrated high potential to drive demand for clean technologies. The methodology's structured approach, emphasis on replication, and grounding in local co-design reflect many of the core principles of ISO 37101, making ICC a cornerstone initiative for standards-based urban innovation.

To support a rapid decarbonisation in settlements, the EU aims to develop at least 100 **Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)** by 2025. The recent series of projects strongly emphasises the integration of digital twins and other digital solutions to support this aim. The **mission-driven projects on PEDs** contribute to emissions reductions in the building and mobility sectors. **PEDs** are urban areas that generate at least as much energy as they consume annually and integrate into broader energy systems. The **TIPS4PED** project supports cities in Italy, Greece, Hungary, and Ireland by providing a digital twin-powered Integrated Assessment Platform (IAP) that incorporates social, technical, regulatory, and financial dimensions. The project's strong emphasis on co-creation, data interoperability, and behavioural change aligns it closely with ongoing European standardisation work. Likewise, **BIPED** is piloting a solar potential calculator and district-level digital twin in Aarhus, Denmark, using open standards such as CityGML and DCAT-AP. Conversely, the project **PROBONO** is advancing the concept of **Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs)** in six Living Labs, aiming for an approach beyond energy. The project's tools explicitly map city actions to the ISO 37101 framework, reinforcing its relevance as a standard for integrated urban sustainability planning. Not part of the Ad hoc Group case studies, but requiring a mention is the **Smart Cities Marketplace (SCM)**. It brings the finance and investment aspects into the picture. Creating an environment to bring together cities, industries, SMEs, investors, researchers and other smart city actors. The SCM offers support to cities using a project maturity level (PML) model, helping the finance community to assess the bankability of city project proposals.

To advance the twin transition in Europe, the replicability of innovative solutions plays a crucial role in knowledge valorisation. The previous section outlined these, as well as the needs and advancements, on a local level.

■ Analysis and mapping

The identified resources for the green and digital transformation of Europe's cities and communities were mapped against the existing standards at the international, European and national levels. This mapping highlights a **strategic opportunity for CEN/TC 465** to serve as a steward for Europe's place-based urban innovation by building a bridge between **locally validated methodologies** and **formally adopted standards** that support EU-wide coherence.

Instrument	Theme	Relevant Standards (ISO / IEC / ITU / National)	Gap or Opportunity
Climate City Contract (CCC) and Local Green Deals (LGD)	Governance, systemic transition	<i>ISO 37101, UNI 11965, DIN SPEC 91637, DIN SPEC 91627, ITU-T Y.4505</i>	Currently, no national ² or international standard directly addresses city-level climate governance contracts, presenting an opportunity to develop a standard or extend existing standards to include contract-based decarbonization planning formally.
Impact Pathways	Transition logic, storytelling	<i>IEC SRD 63235 (Concept Methodology), DIN SPEC 91637</i>	Existing standards lack robust models for systems transformation narratives. Potential to build IEC/ISO guidance or a CWA based on ICC methodology.
Monitoring Indicators	Evaluation and metrics	<i>ITU-T Y.4505, ITU-T Y.4900–4909, ISO 37120–23, ISO 37125, ISO 14060 family, PAS 2070, DIN SPEC 91627, DIN SPEC 91637</i>	Opportunity to integrate climate-specific KPIs and decarbonisation tracking into existing indicator standards. Cities struggle to define SMART indicators.
Transition Map	Decarbonisation roadmaps	<i>ISO 37101, IEC SRD 63273, ISO/IEC 30182</i>	Existing use-case standards are generic. Project outputs (e.g. NZC, TIPS4PED) could form the basis for roadmap-oriented technical specifications.
Local Green Deal Blueprint	Multi-stakeholder action, co-governance	<i>ISO 37101, IEC TR on Standards Collaboration, UNI 11965, UNE 178301</i>	Governance and stakeholder participation standards are fragmented. The Blueprint could help define a structured, replicable approach. Supports ISO 37101 updates.

² There is a national standard in the making by the Cypriot Standards Institute closely linking to the CCC.

Having had more insights into existing blueprints, their integration into the work plan of relevant European SDOs would be helpful:

Theme	Coverage in Standards	Standardisation Potential
Governance Models (CCC, LGDs)	Partial	High - inform new IEC/ITU process or policy standards
Indicators & Evaluation	Covered	High - augment with climate-neutral KPIs
Transition Mapping & Pathways	Partial	Medium-High - could be added to use case libraries
Citizen Co-creation / Engagement	Lacking	High - no existing standard addresses citizen-led design in the analysed dataset.
Systemic Urban Planning for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities	Partial	Medium - some coverage via IEC SRD 63320, but not tailored to climate neutrality

Standards which address core topics in the presented case studies and initiatives are highlighted below:

Standard	Focus Area	Relevant to	Gap / Opportunity
ISO 37101	Sustainable community management	<i>CCC, LGDs, R&I Projects</i>	Serves as a baseline for integrated city governance. Extend to include LGD/CCC methodologies.
ISO 37120 / 37122 / 37123	KPIs for smart, resilient cities	<i>Monitoring Indicators, PEDs</i>	Can be expanded with environmental and climate neutrality indicators from Horizon outputs.
ISO/IEC 30182	Smart city data ontology	<i>Transition Map, CitiVerse, PED and Mission Projects</i>	Basis for standardising digital twin semantics. Could be harmonised with DIN SPEC 91607, UNE 178104.
DIN SPEC 91607	Digital twins for cities	<i>LDT Toolbox, EDIC, CitiVerse, PED and Mission Projects</i>	Valuable national input to broader IEC or ISO standardisation of urban digital twins.

Standard	Focus Area	Relevant to	Gap / Opportunity
UNI 11965:2024	Stakeholder involvement in local governance	<i>LGDs, CCC</i>	Fills the participation gap, aligns with ISO 37101—high potential for European harmonisation.
UNE 178104:2017	Interoperability for smart city platforms	<i>LDT Toolbox, EDIC, CitiVerse, PED and Mission Projects</i>	Supports digital twin and platform integration , highly aligned with EU digital policy goals.
UNE 178301:2015	Open data and citizen engagement	<i>LGDs, Smart Communities Network</i>	Supports transparency and co-creation. It could be adopted more broadly across EU cities.
ITU-T Y.4505	Minimal interoperability mechanisms for smart and sustainable cities and communities	<i>LDT Toolbox, EDIC, CitiVerse, PED and Mission Projects</i>	Supports interoperability of solutions depending on data.
ITU-T Y.4900 series	KPIs and smart city evaluation	<i>NZC, Monitoring Indicators</i>	Strong base, but requires updates to meet climate neutrality dimensions (e.g., ISO IWA 42/48 integration).
IEC SRD 63520	Energy challenge and systems approach	<i>PED, NZC and Mission Projects</i>	Key for aligning digital energy platforms with urban resilience goals.
ISO 23386 / 23387	Building data templates	<i>PED and Mission Projects, UNI 11973</i>	Relevant for the built environment lifecycle and digital twin integration.

CWA 18125 and CWA 18245 are recognised in CEN/CLC/JTC 25 - Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud, and Edge, and are therefore not mentioned here.

■ Conclusions

The Ad hoc Group mobilises the essential resources needed to achieve the green and digital transformation of Europe's cities and communities. The results demonstrate that the intersection of European policy frameworks, such as the **EU Cities Mission**, the **Green Deal**, and the **Digital Decade**, with the standard-developing ecosystems offers an opportunity to advance the joint consideration of climate-neutral and smart cities. Through the mapping of international (ISO, IEC, ITU), national (DIN, UNE, UNI), and initiative-derived frameworks (e.g. CCCs, LGDs, PEDs), the pivotal role of standards as enablers in scaling up and sustaining local transformation efforts across Europe is highlighted.

This commitment provides a robust and unified European answer to the demands of the international stage. As integrated methodologies, such as the **Local Green Deal Blueprint** and **Climate City Contracts (CCC)**, mature through real-world implementation, their potential alignment with frameworks like **ISO 37101** and complementary indicator standards becomes increasingly evident. Standardisation can enhance **replicability, comparability**, and long-term **institutional legacy**, particularly when grounded in the lived experiences and practical needs of cities and communities.

Examples ranging from **Positive Energy District pilots** to **local data governance infrastructures** highlight the high replication potential of solutions designed within structured, inclusive frameworks being developed and tested by our cities and communities. However, recurring challenges, such as fragmented data ecosystems, capacity limitations, and the lack of harmonised implementation tools, continue to hinder widespread adoption across the LRGs.

Meanwhile, the accelerating momentum of initiatives related to **nature-based solutions, digitalisation**, and **urban resilience** reflects the growing maturity of Europe's research and innovation ecosystem. These efforts are converging around common goals, yet they still require the **binding coherence** that only formal standards can provide. In this light, standards emerge as the vital bridge between **experimental innovation** and **institutional transformation**.

The presented collective effort aims to develop a coordinated European response to global challenges and international proposals, such as those being brought forward within ISO/TC 268 WG1 by China and ISO/TC 268 WG2 by South Korea.

We, the Ad hoc Group, therefore, recommend that the insights, methodologies, and tools developed within EU-funded projects be systematically considered for formal integration into the European and international standardisation landscape, whether through updates to established frameworks such as **ISO 37101**, new work items under **CEN/TC 465**, or interim instruments such as **CWAs (CEN Workshop Agreements)**.

We, the Ad hoc Group convenors, extend our sincere thanks to all experts, stakeholders, and guest contributors whose insights, commitment, and collaboration have made this journey both meaningful and successful. Your contributions have not only informed this report but have helped shape a shared vision for the future of Europe's cities and communities. We thank the CEN/TC 465 for the trust in this work. We implore **the leadership of CEN/TC 465** to champion these findings and advocate for action in the relevant circles. Strategic alignment and leadership within relevant European and international fora will be essential to ensure Europe's local innovations underpin **Europe's resilience and position**.

■ Annex

■ Dates and overview

September 19, 2024	Kick-off, hybrid meeting in Berlin
October 31, 2025	Framework development to integrate relevant outcomes and initiatives, sharing the call for case studies
November 21, 2024	Case study presentations and first overview of relevant standards
December 12, 2024	Case study presentations and report structure
January 31, 2025	Case study presentations
February 20, 2025	Case study presentations, insights into future standards on digital twins and the Paris AI summit
March 10, 2025	Policy embedment and European Semester, case study presentations
April 29, 2025	Positive Energy Districts and case study presentations
June 03, 2025	Conclusion: hybrid meeting in Copenhagen

Recommendation Committee and its respective mirror committees

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